

**SUMS OF $\omega(n)$ AND $\Omega(n)$ OVER THE k -FREE PARTS AND
 k -FULL PARTS OF SOME PARTICULAR SEQUENCES**

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Abstract

The k -free part of a positive integer n is the product of the prime powers dividing n that have exponent less than k in the factorization, while the k -full part of n is the product of the prime powers that have exponent at least k . We consider sums of the prime factor counting functions ω and Ω going over the k -free parts and k -full parts of some particular number sequences.

1. Introduction

For a positive integer with prime factorization

$$n = q_1^{s_1} \cdots q_r^{s_r}, \quad (1)$$

where the q_j are the prime factors and the $s_j \geq 1$ are their respective exponents, the prime factor counting functions are defined by $\omega(n) = r$ and $\Omega(n) = s_1 + \cdots + s_r$.

For $k \geq 1$, and n as above, let

$$L_k(n) = \prod_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq r \\ s_j < k}} q_j^{s_j} \quad \text{and} \quad U_k(n) = \prod_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq r \\ k \leq s_j}} q_j^{s_j}.$$

We say that $L_k(n)$ is the k -free part of n and that $U_k(n)$ is the k -full part of n . By convention, $L_1(n) = 1$, while naturally $U_1(n) = n$. Similarly, when $k > \max_j s_j$, we have $L_k(n) = n$ and $U_k(n) = 1$. We remark that $n = L_k(n)U_k(n)$ for any k and that $L_k(n)$ and $U_k(n)$ are coprime. The case of $k = 2$ was considered by Cloutier, De Koninck, and Doyon [2].

The aim of this article is to consider sums of ω and Ω composed with U_k and L_k evaluated in certain sequences of positive integer numbers.

To begin, we consider the evaluation in the whole sequence of positive integer numbers.

Theorem 1. *Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer. We have that*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(U_k(n)) = \left(\sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} \right) x + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right), \tag{2}$$

and

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(U_k(n)) = \left(\sum_p \frac{1 - k + kp}{p^{k+1} - p^k} \right) x + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right), \tag{3}$$

where the sums over p indicate that the sums are taken over all prime numbers.

For the rest of this article we will continue to use the convention that sums and products over p indicate over all the primes, unless stated otherwise.

Corollary 1. *Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer. We have that*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(L_k(n)) = x \log \log x + \left(B_1 - \sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} \right) x + O \left(\frac{x}{\log x} \right), \tag{4}$$

where B_1 is the Mertens constant given by

$$B_1 = \gamma + \sum_p \left(\log \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) + \frac{1}{p} \right), \tag{5}$$

and $\gamma = 0.57721\dots$ is the Euler–Mascheroni constant.

We have that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(L_k(n)) = x \log \log x + \left(B_2 - \sum_p \frac{1 - k + kp}{p^{k+1} - p^k} \right) x + O \left(\frac{x}{\log x} \right), \tag{6}$$

where

$$B_2 = B_1 + \sum_p \frac{1}{p(p-1)}. \tag{7}$$

Let $h \geq 1$ be an integer. A positive integer n is said to be h -free if all its prime factors have exponents less than h . In other words, if n has prime factorization (1), then $s_j \leq h - 1$ for all j . In particular, n is square-free if all $s_j = 1$. We denote by \mathcal{S}_h the set of h -free positive integers.

We have the following result.

Theorem 2. *Let $h > k > 1$ be integers. Then we have*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} D_{\Omega,k,h} x + O_h \left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{k^2}} \log \log x \right), \tag{8}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \omega(U_k(n)) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} D_{\omega,k,h} x + O_h \left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{k^2}} \log \log x \right). \tag{9}$$

where

$$D_{\Omega,k,h} = \sum_p \frac{h-1 - (k-1)p^{h-k} - hp + kp^{h-k+1}}{(p-1)(p^h-1)}, \tag{10}$$

and

$$D_{\omega,k,h} = \sum_p \frac{p^{h-k} - 1}{p^h - 1}. \tag{11}$$

Corollary 2. *Let $h > k > 1$ be integers. Then we have*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(L_k(n)) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} x \log \log x + O(x), \tag{12}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \omega(L_k(n)) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} x \log \log x + O(x). \tag{13}$$

Let $h \geq 1$ be an integer. A positive integer n is said to be h -full if all its prime factors have exponents greater or equal than h . In other words, if n has prime factorization (1), then $s_j \geq h$ for all j . (This definition is trivial for $h = 1$.) We denote by \mathcal{N}_h the set of h -full positive integers.

We prove the following estimates.

Theorem 3. *Let $k > h > 0$ be integers. Then we have*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) = \gamma_{0,h} E_{\Omega,k,h} x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{h} - (\frac{k}{h} - 1) \frac{1}{k+2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} \log \log x \right), \tag{14}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \omega(U_k(n)) = \gamma_{0,h} E_{\omega,k,h} x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{h} - (\frac{k}{h} - 1) \frac{1}{k+2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} \log \log x \right), \tag{15}$$

where

$$\gamma_{0,h} = \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p - p^{\frac{1}{h}}}{p^2 (p^{\frac{1}{h}} - 1)} \right), \tag{16}$$

$$E_{\Omega,k,h} = \sum_p \frac{kp^{\frac{1}{h}} - k + 1}{p^{\frac{k-h-1}{h}} (p^{\frac{1}{h}} - 1) (p^{1+\frac{1}{h}} + p^{\frac{1}{h}} - p)}, \tag{17}$$

and

$$E_{\omega,k,h} = \sum_p \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k-h-1}{h}} (p^{1+\frac{1}{h}} + p^{\frac{1}{h}} - p)}. \tag{18}$$

Corollary 3. *Let $k > h > 0$ be integers. The following formula holds:*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(L_k(n)) = h\gamma_{0,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}} \log \log x + \gamma_{0,h} (C_{\Omega,h} - E_{\omega,k,h})x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O_h \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{h}}}{\sqrt{\log x}} \right), \tag{19}$$

where

$$C_{\Omega,h} = h(B_2 - \log h) + \sum_p \frac{(h+1)p^{1+\frac{1}{h}} - hp - 2hp^{\frac{2}{h}} + (2h-1)p^{\frac{1}{h}}}{(p-1)(p^{\frac{1}{h}}-1)(p^{1+\frac{1}{h}}+p^{\frac{1}{h}}-p)}. \tag{20}$$

Corollary 3 is deduced from an estimate for the first moment of $\Omega(n)$ over h -full numbers that was computed in [8, Theorem 2]. It would be interesting to obtain an analogous result for $\omega(n)$. To do this, we would need to use different techniques than the ones employed in the proof of [8, Theorem 2], which rely in the total multiplicativity of $\Omega(n)$. See [9, Section 6] for a discussion of this issue in the function field case.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 includes the proof of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1 by elementary counting, as well as a corollary considering the sum going over h -powers. Theorem 2 is proven in Section 3. This is achieved by counting first the h -free integers that are coprime to certain fixed number. Corollary 2 is obtained as a consequence of known results for the count over all h -free numbers. Finally, Section 4 contains a proof of Theorem 3, which follows from counting integers that are simultaneously h -free and k -full, while Corollary 3 is obtained as a consequence of known results for the count over all h -full numbers.

2. Sums over Integers

In this section we prove Theorem 1. We start by recalling the following results involving sums of primes.

Lemma 1. [1, Lemma 1.2] *If $s > 1$,*

$$\sum_{p \geq x} \frac{1}{p^s} = \frac{1}{(s-1)x^{s-1} \log x} + O \left(\frac{1}{x^{s-1} \log^2 x} \right).$$

Lemma 2. [1, Lemma 1.4] If $r, s \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{p^s}{\log^r p} = \frac{x^{s+1}}{(s+1) \log^{r+1} x} + O\left(\frac{x^{s+1}}{\log^{r+2} x}\right).$$

Proof of Theorem 1. We consider Equation (2). Notice that summing over all the numbers of the form $\omega(U_k(n))$ is equivalent to counting the number of powers $p^\ell \leq x$ such that $\ell \geq k$, and each power must be counted with multiplicity equal to the number of $n \leq x$ such that $p^\ell \mid n$. But this is equivalent to counting the multiples of p^k that are less than or equal to x . In other words, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(U_k(n)) = \sum_{p^k \leq x} \left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^k} \right\rfloor = \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{x}{p^k} - \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \left\{ \frac{x}{p^k} \right\}.$$

Applying the Prime Number Theorem as well as Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \omega(U_k(n)) &= x \sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} - x \sum_{p > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{1}{p^k} + O_k\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x}\right) \\ &= x \sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} + O_k\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Equation (3) is proven similarly. Summing over all the numbers of the form $\Omega(U_k(n))$ is equivalent to counting the number of powers $p^\ell \leq x$ such that $\ell \geq k$, and each power must be counted with multiplicity equal to the number of $n \leq x$ such that $p^\ell \mid n$ but $p^{\ell+1} \nmid n$, multiplied by ℓ . Set $t = \lfloor \log_p x \rfloor$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= \sum_{p^k \leq x} \sum_{\ell=k}^t \ell \left(\left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^\ell} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^{\ell+1}} \right\rfloor \right) \\ &= \sum_{p^k \leq x} \left(k \left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^k} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^{k+1}} \right\rfloor + \dots + \left\lfloor \frac{x}{p^t} \right\rfloor \right) \\ &= x \sum_{p^k \leq x} \left(\frac{k}{p^k} + \frac{1}{p^{k+1}} + \dots + \frac{1}{p^t} \right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{p^k \leq x} \left(k \left\{ \frac{x}{p^k} \right\} + \left\{ \frac{x}{p^{k+1}} \right\} + \dots + \left\{ \frac{x}{p^t} \right\} \right) \\ &= x \sum_{p^k \leq x} \left(\frac{\frac{1}{p^{k+1}} - \frac{1}{p^{t+1}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p}} + \frac{k}{p^k} \right) + O\left(\sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} t\right) \\ &= x \sum_{p^k \leq x} \frac{\frac{1-k}{p^{k+1}} - \frac{1}{p^{t+1}} + \frac{k}{p^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{p}} + O\left(\log x \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{1}{\log p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Now we use the Prime Number Theorem to estimate

$$x \sum_{p^k \leq x} \frac{1}{p^{k+1}(1 - \frac{1}{p})} \ll x \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{1}{x} \ll_k \frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x}.$$

By applying the above estimate as well as Lemmas 1 and 2 (with $r = 1, s = 0$), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= x \sum_p \frac{\frac{1-k}{p^{k+1}} + \frac{k}{p^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{p}} - x \sum_{p > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\frac{1-k}{p^{k+1}} + \frac{k}{p^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{p}} + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right) \\ &= x \sum_p \frac{1 - k + kp}{p^{k+1} - p^k} + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Theorem 1. □

Proof of Corollary 1. To prove Equations (4) and (6) we use the well-known identities [5, Theorem 430] and [4, Section 1.4.4]) for $x \geq 2$:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(n) = x \log \log x + B_1 x + O \left(\frac{x}{\log x} \right), \tag{21}$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(n) = x \log \log x + B_2 x + O \left(\frac{x}{\log x} \right), \tag{22}$$

where B_1 and B_2 are given by Equations (5) and (7) respectively.

Notice that $\Omega(n) = \Omega(L_k(n)) + \Omega(U_k(n))$ and, since $L_k(n)$ and $U_k(n)$ are co-prime, $\omega(n) = \omega(L_k(n)) + \omega(U_k(n))$ as well. Combining Equations (2) and (3) with Equations (21) and (22), we get Equations (4) and (6). □

A perfect power is a number of the form n^h , where $h \geq 2$ and n are positive integers. We can immediately deduce the following result from Theorem 1.

Corollary 4. *Let $k \geq 2$ be an integer. The following formulas hold:*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n^h \leq x} \Omega(U_k(n^h)) &= h \left(\sum_p \frac{1 - k + kp}{p^{k+1} - p^k} \right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O_{k,h} \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{hk}}}{\log x} \right), \\ \sum_{n^h \leq x} \omega(U_k(n^h)) &= \left(\sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} \right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O_{k,h} \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{hk}}}{\log x} \right). \end{aligned}$$

In addition, the following formulas hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n^h \leq x} \Omega(L_k(n^h)) &= hx^{\frac{1}{h}} \log \log x + h \left(B_2 - \log h - \sum_p \frac{1-k+kp}{p^{k+1}-p^k} \right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} \\ &\quad + O_h \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{h}}}{\log x} \right), \\ \sum_{n^h \leq x} \omega(L_k(n^h)) &= x^{\frac{1}{h}} \log \log x + \left(B_1 - \log h - \sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} \right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O_h \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{h}}}{\log x} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let $\omega_k(n)$ be the number of primes with exponent k in the prime factorization of n .

Corollary 5. *Let $k \geq 1$ be an integer. We have the asymptotic formula*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega_k(n) = \left(\sum_p \frac{p-1}{p^{k+1}} \right) x + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right).$$

This recovers a result of Elma and Liu [3], who also studied the second moment of ω_k .

Proof. By Equation (2), we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega_k(n) = \sum_{n \leq x} \omega(U_k(n)) - \omega(U_{k+1}(n)) = x \left(\sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} - \sum_p \frac{1}{p^{k+1}} \right) + O_k \left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\log x} \right),$$

and the result follows. □

Remark 1. It is interesting to consider the quotient of the sums appearing in Equations (2) and (3). We get

$$\frac{\sum_{n \leq x} \Omega(U_k(n))}{\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(U_k(n))} \rightarrow \frac{\sum_p \frac{1-k+kp}{p^{k+1}-p^k}}{\sum_p \frac{1}{p^k}}. \tag{23}$$

Since we have that

$$\frac{k}{p^k} = \frac{k(p-1)}{p^k(p-1)} < \frac{kp-(k-1)}{p^k(p-1)} \leq \frac{(k+1)(p-1)}{p^k(p-1)} = \frac{k+1}{p^k},$$

and the second inequality is strict for $p > 2$, we conclude that the limit (23) belongs to the interval $(k, k+1)$.

Remark 2. The constants appearing in Equations (2) and (3) can also be expressed as

$$\sum_p \frac{1}{p^k} = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\omega(U)}{U} \tag{24}$$

and

$$\sum_p \frac{1 - k + kp}{p^{k+1} - p^k} = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{p|n} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U}. \tag{25}$$

This can be seen by working with the generating functions, in a method that will be employed to find the constants in Theorems 2 and 3. In fact, Equations (24) and (25) can be obtained from $D_{\omega,k,h}$ and Equation (30) as well as $D_{\Omega,k,h}$ and Equation (29) by letting $h \rightarrow \infty$ and therefore removing the condition h -free.

3. Sums over h -Free Numbers

In this section we prove Theorem 2. We start with the following estimate for the number of k -free positive integers that are not divisible by some fixed primes.

Lemma 3. *Let q_1, \dots, q_r be prime numbers, and let $\mathfrak{Q}_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x)$ be the number of k -free positive integers not exceeding x such that they are relatively prime to $q_1 \dots q_r$. The following formula holds:*

$$\mathfrak{Q}_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(\frac{1 - \frac{1}{q_j}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^k}} \right) x + O_k \left(2^r x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right).$$

We remark that the above formula generalizes the classical estimate giving

$$Q_k(x) = \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right),$$

where $Q_k(x)$ is the number of k -free numbers not exceeding x .

Proof. Consider the modified Möbius function defined as

$$\mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) = \begin{cases} \mu(d) & (d, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

By Möbius inversion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{Q}_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) &= \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_k \\ n \leq x \\ (n, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1}} 1 = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ (n, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1}} \sum_{\substack{d^k | n \\ (d, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1}} \mu(d) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ (n, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1}} \sum_{d^k | n} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d). \end{aligned}$$

Writing $n = d^k e$, we have

$$\Omega_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) = \sum_{d^k \leq x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \sum_{\substack{e \leq x/d^k \\ (e, q_1 \dots q_r) = 1}} 1.$$

Estimating the inner sum with inclusion-exclusion, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) &= \sum_{d^k \leq x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \left(\left\lfloor \frac{x}{d^k} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{x}{q_i d^k} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{x}{q_i q_j d^k} \right\rfloor + \dots \right) \\ &= \sum_{d^k \leq x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \frac{x}{d^k} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right) \\ &\quad + O \left(\sum_{d^k \leq x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \left(\left\{ \frac{x}{d^k} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{x}{q_i d^k} \right\} + \left\{ \frac{x}{q_i q_j d^k} \right\} + \dots \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{d^k \leq x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \frac{x}{d^k} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right) + O \left(2^r \sum_{d^k \leq x} 1 \right). \end{aligned}$$

After using the full sum to estimate, the above becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_d \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \frac{x}{d^k} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right) - \sum_{d^k > x} \mu_{q_1 \dots q_r}(d) \frac{x}{d^k} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right) + O \left(2^r x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right) \\ &= x \prod_{p \neq q_j} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right) + O \left(x \sum_{d^k > x} \frac{1}{d^k} \right) + O \left(2^r x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Estimating the first big- O term by approximating with an integral, we obtain $O_k(x^{\frac{1}{k}})$, and this yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{k,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) &= x \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j^k} \right)} + O_k \left(2^r x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{q_j^k} \right)} x + O_k \left(2^r x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

□

We now state some results involving sums of prime factor counting functions over h -full numbers that will be needed for the proofs of Theorem 2 and Corollary 2.

Theorem 4. *Let $h \geq 1$ be an integer. We have*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(n) = h\gamma_{0,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}} \log \log x + \gamma_{0,h}C_{\Omega,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O_h\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1}{h}}}{\sqrt{\log x}}\right), \tag{26}$$

where $\gamma_{0,h}$ is given by Equation (16) and $C_{\Omega,h}$ is given by Equation (20).

We omit the proof, since Equation (26) was proven in [8, Theorem 2].

Lemma 4. *Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. Then, we have*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ x < n \leq y}} \Omega(n)n^\alpha = O_h\left(y^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log y\right) + O_h\left(x^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log x\right).$$

and

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ x < n \leq y}} \omega(n)n^\alpha = O_h\left(y^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log y\right) + O_h\left(x^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log x\right).$$

Proof. Denote

$$\mathcal{N}_h(x) = \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(n),$$

and remark that the asymptotics for $\mathcal{N}_h(x)$ is given by Equation (26).

By Abel’s summation formula,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ x < n \leq y}} \Omega(n)n^\alpha &= \mathcal{N}_h(y)y^\alpha - \mathcal{N}_h(x)x^\alpha - \alpha \int_x^y \mathcal{N}_h(t)t^{\alpha-1} dt \\ &= h\gamma_{0,h}y^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log y - h\gamma_{0,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log x \\ &\quad + O\left(y^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha}\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha}\right) + O\left(\int_x^y t^{\alpha-\frac{h-1}{h}} \log \log t dt\right) \\ &= O_h\left(y^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log y\right) + O_h\left(x^{\frac{1}{h}+\alpha} \log \log x\right). \end{aligned}$$

The estimate for the sum over $\omega(n)$ can be deduced from the fact that $\omega(n) \leq \Omega(n)$. □

Proof of Theorem 2. We prove Equations (8) and (10). Fix $0 < B \leq x$ (to be determined later) and suppose that $U = U_k(n)$ is such that $U \leq B$. We start by counting all the possible values of $L = L_k(n)$ satisfying $L \leq x/U$. By Lemma 3, the number of possible values of L is given by

$$\Omega_{k,q_1,\dots,q_r}\left(\frac{x}{U}\right) = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(\frac{q_j^k - q_j^{k-1}}{q_j^k - 1}\right) \frac{x}{U} + O\left(2^r \frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{U^{\frac{1}{k}}}\right),$$

where q_1, \dots, q_r are the primes in the factorization of U . Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x \\ U_k(n) \leq B}} \Omega(U_k(n)) + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) \\ &= \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h \\ U \leq B}} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U} \\ &\quad + O \left(\sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h \\ U \leq B}} \Omega(U) 2^{\omega(U)} \frac{x^{\frac{1}{k}}}{U^{\frac{1}{k}}} \right) + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that for $U \in \mathcal{N}_k$, we have $2^{\omega(U)} \leq q_1 \cdots q_r \leq U^{\frac{1}{k}}$. Using this to bound the error term gives

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U} + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h \\ U \leq B}} \Omega(U) \right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) - \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h \\ B < U}} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U}. \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

We have the following estimate

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) \leq \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h \\ B < U \leq x}} \left\lfloor \frac{x}{U} \right\rfloor \Omega(U) \leq \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ U \leq x}} \frac{x}{U} \Omega(U). \tag{28}$$

Applying Lemma 4 to Equations (27) and (28), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U} + O_h \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} B^{\frac{1}{k}} \log \log B \right) \\ &\quad + O_h \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \log \log x \right) + O_h \left(x B^{\frac{1}{k}-1} \log \log B \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let $B = x^{1-\frac{1}{k}}$. We get

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) = \frac{x}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U} + O_h \left(x^{\frac{2k-1}{k^2}} \log \log x \right).$$

We now proceed to find a closed expression for

$$\frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\Omega(U)}{U}. \tag{29}$$

We consider a generating function given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\Omega,k,h}(z) &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \frac{z^{\Omega(n)}}{n} \prod_{q|n} \frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{z^k}{p^k} \left(1 + \frac{z}{p} + \dots + \frac{z^{h-k-1}}{p^{h-k-1}} \right) \right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{\frac{z^h}{p^h} - \frac{z^k}{p^k}}{\frac{z}{p} - 1} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which is absolutely convergent over compact sets.

We will recover our term of interest from considering $\mathcal{D}'_{\Omega,k,h}(1)$. In order to find this term, we consider the logarithmic derivative of $\mathcal{D}_{\Omega,k,h}(z)$:

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\Omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{D}_{\Omega,k,h}(z)} = \sum_p \frac{\left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \left((h-1) \frac{z^h}{p^{h+1}} - (k-1) \frac{z^k}{p^{k+1}} - h \frac{z^{h-1}}{p^h} + k \frac{z^{k-1}}{p^k} \right)}{\left(\frac{z}{p} - 1 \right)^2 \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{\frac{z^h}{p^h} - \frac{z^k}{p^k}}{\frac{z}{p} - 1} \right)}.$$

Evaluating at $z = 1$, we obtain,

$$\left. \frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\Omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{D}_{\Omega,k,h}(z)} \right|_{z=1} = \sum_p \frac{\left(\frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \right) \left(\frac{h-1}{p^{h+1}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{k+1}} - \frac{h}{p^h} + \frac{k}{p^k} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \left(1 - \frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \right)}.$$

Multiplying the above by $\mathcal{D}_{\Omega,k,h}(1)$ and by the coefficient $\frac{1}{\zeta(k)} = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)$ provides the coefficient for the main term of (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\Omega,k,h}(1)}{\zeta(k)} &= \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_p \frac{\left(\frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \right) \left(\frac{h-1}{p^{h+1}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{k+1}} - \frac{h}{p^h} + \frac{k}{p^k} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \left(1 - \frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \right)} \\ &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 - \left(\frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{\frac{h-1}{p^{h+1}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{k+1}} - \frac{h}{p^h} + \frac{k}{p^k}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^h} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} \sum_p \frac{h - 1 - (k-1)p^{h-k} - hp + kp^{h-k+1}}{(p-1)(p^h - 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Equations (9) and (11) are proven analogously. Here the difference is that we must consider instead

$$\frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \prod_{q|U} \left(\frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \right) \frac{\omega(U)}{U}, \tag{30}$$

while the error term can be bounded as in the Ω case, using the fact that $\omega(n) \leq \Omega(n)$.

In this case the generating function is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\omega,k,h}(z) &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_k \cap \mathcal{S}_h} \frac{z^{\omega(n)}}{n} \prod_{q|n} \frac{q^k - q^{k-1}}{q^k - 1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{z}{p^k} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p} + \dots + \frac{1}{p^{h-k-1}} \right) \right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{z \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)}{\frac{1}{p} - 1} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which is absolutely convergent.

In order to find $\mathcal{D}'_{\omega,k,h}(1)$, we consider the logarithmic derivative:

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{D}_{\omega,k,h}(z)} = \sum_p \frac{\left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{\left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)}{\frac{1}{p} - 1}}{1 + \left(\frac{p^k - p^{k-1}}{p^k - 1} \right) \frac{z \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)}{\frac{1}{p} - 1}}.$$

Therefore,

$$\left. \frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{D}_{\omega,k,h}(z)} \right|_{z=1} = \sum_p \frac{p^{h-k} - 1}{p^h - 1}.$$

Multiplying the above by $\mathcal{D}_{\omega,k,h}(1)$ and by the coefficient $\frac{1}{\zeta(k)} = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k} \right)$ yields the coefficient for the main term of Equation (9):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{D}'_{\omega,k,h}(1)}{\zeta(k)} &= \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_p \frac{p^{h-k} - 1}{p^h - 1} \prod_p \left(1 - \left(\frac{p^k}{p^k - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{p^h} - \frac{1}{p^k} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{p^{h-k} - 1}{p^h - 1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^h} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} \sum_p \frac{p^{h-k} - 1}{p^h - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Theorem 2. □

Theorem 5. *The following asymptotic formulas hold:*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(n) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} x \log \log x + O(x), \tag{31}$$

and

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{S}_h \\ n \leq x}} \omega(n) = \frac{1}{\zeta(h)} x \log \log x + O(x). \tag{32}$$

We omit the proof, since Equation (31) was proven in [8, Theorem 1] and Equation (32) can be proven similarly.

Proof of Corollary 2. Since $n = L_k(n)U_k(n)$, we have $\Omega(n) = \Omega(L_k(n)) + \Omega(U_k(n))$, and similarly with ω (since $L_k(n)$ and $U_k(n)$ are coprime). Combining Equations (8) and (31), we immediately obtain Equation (12). Equation (13) follows by combining Equations (9) and (32). \square

4. Sums over h -Full Numbers

In this section we prove Theorem 3. Before proceeding to the proof, we need the following generalization of Lemma 3.

Lemma 5. *Let q_1, \dots, q_r be prime numbers and let $k > h$ be integers. We define $\mathfrak{Q}_{k,h,q_1 \dots q_r}(x)$ as the number of k -free, h -full positive integers not exceeding x such that they are relatively prime to $q_1 \dots q_r$. The following formula holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{Q}_{k,h,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q_j} - \frac{1}{q_j^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^h}} \right)^{-1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^k}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^h}} \right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} \\ &\quad + O\left(2^r x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrarily small.

Proof. Consider the generating function

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \cap \mathcal{S}_k \\ (n, q_1 \cdots q_r) = 1}} \frac{1}{n^s} &= \prod_{p \neq q_j} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{sh}} + \cdots + \frac{1}{p^{s(k-1)}} \right) \\ &= \prod_{p \neq q_j} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{sh}} - \frac{1}{p^{sk}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}} \right) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j^{sh}} \right)^{-1} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{sh}} \right) \prod_{p \neq q_j} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{s(h+1)}} - \frac{1}{p^{sk}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{sh}}\right)} \right) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j^{sh}} \right)^{-1} \frac{\zeta(sh)}{\zeta(2sh)} \mathcal{H}_{q_1 \cdots q_r}(s). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that for $\text{Re}(s) > \frac{1}{h+1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{H}_{q_1 \cdots q_r}(s)| &\leq \prod_{p \neq q_j} \left(1 + \left| \frac{\frac{1}{p^{s(h+1)}} - \frac{1}{p^{sk}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{sh}}\right)} \right| \right) \\ &\leq \prod_p \left(1 + \left| \frac{\frac{1}{p^{s(h+1)}} - \frac{1}{p^{sk}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{sh}}\right)} \right| \right), \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

which is convergent for $\text{Re}(s) \geq \frac{1}{h+1} + \varepsilon$, and therefore $\mathcal{H}_{q_1 \cdots q_r}(s)$ is convergent for $\text{Re}(s) > \frac{1}{h+1}$. Now we use Perron's formula ([10, Section 5.1], [11, Section 4.4], more precisely, Problems 4.4.15-4.4.17). Take $\sigma_0 = \frac{1}{h} + \varepsilon$. As $T \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{k,h,q_1 \cdots q_r}(x) &= \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \cap \mathcal{S}_k \\ n \leq x \\ (n, q_1 \cdots q_r) = 1}} 1 \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\sigma_0 - iT}^{\sigma_0 + iT} \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j^{sh}} \right)^{-1} \frac{\zeta(sh)}{\zeta(2sh)} \mathcal{H}_{q_1 \cdots q_r}(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + O\left(\frac{x^{\sigma_0 + \varepsilon}}{T}\right). \end{aligned}$$

To compute this integral we consider the rectangle of vertical sides $[\sigma_0 - iT, \sigma_0 + iT]$ and $[\sigma_1 - iT, \sigma_1 + iT]$ and horizontal sides $[\sigma_0 \pm iT, \sigma_1 \pm iT]$. The integral over the sides is equal to the residue from the pole at $s = \frac{1}{h}$, which can be computed as

follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j}\right)^{-1} \frac{h}{\zeta(2)} \mathcal{H}_{q_1 \dots q_r} \left(\frac{1}{h}\right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} \operatorname{Res}_{s=\frac{1}{h}} \zeta(sh) \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q_j} - \frac{1}{q_j^{\frac{1}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}+1}} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}\right) x^{\frac{1}{h}}. \end{aligned}$$

Since we are interested in the integral over the segment $[\sigma_0 - iT, \sigma_0 + iT]$, we proceed to bound the integral at the vertical segment $[\sigma_1 - iT, \sigma_1 + iT]$ and at the horizontal lines $[\sigma_0 \pm iT, \sigma_1 \pm iT]$. First we note that Inequality (33) gives a uniform bound for $\mathcal{H}_{q_1 \dots q_r}(s)$ which is independent of the choice of q_1, \dots, q_r . Next notice that we have, over the same segments,

$$\left|1 + \frac{1}{q^{sh}}\right|^{-1} \leq \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\operatorname{Re}(s)h}}} \leq \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}} \leq \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{2}}}},$$

and the above bound is less than or equal to 2 when $q \neq 2, 3$, and for $q = 2, 3$ it is bounded by 4 and 3, respectively. Thus, we have the following bound over the vertical segment $[\sigma_1 - iT, \sigma_1 + iT]$ and at the horizontal lines $[\sigma_0 \pm iT, \sigma_1 \pm iT]$:

$$\left| \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j^{sh}}\right)^{-1} \right| < 12 \cdot 2^r.$$

Since $\zeta(\sigma \pm iT) = O\left(T^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)$ uniformly for $\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1$ as $T \rightarrow \infty$ (see for example, [6, Theorem 1.9]), the horizontal integrals on $[\sigma_0 \pm iT, \sigma_1 \pm iT]$ contribute $O\left(2^r \frac{x^{\sigma_0 T - \frac{1}{2}}}{\log x}\right)$.

The vertical line $[\sigma_1 - iT, \sigma_1 + iT]$ contributes to $O\left(2^r x^{\sigma_1 T^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)$.

Finally, taking $T = x^{\frac{1}{h(h+1)}}$ gives a final estimate of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{Q}_{k,h,q_1 \dots q_r}(x) &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q_j} - \frac{1}{q_j^{\frac{1}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{1}{\zeta(2)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}+1}} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}\right) x^{\frac{1}{h}} \\ &\quad + O\left(2^r x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon}\right). \end{aligned}$$

□

We remark that the main term in Lemma 5 reduces to the main term in Lemma 3 when $h = 1$. However, the error term has size $O\left(2^r x^{\frac{3}{4} + \varepsilon}\right)$ and is worse. The

reason for this is that we are only considering the pole at $s = \frac{1}{h}$ in Perron's formula. To eliminate the dependence on h we would need to remove all the poles up to $\frac{1}{k}$.

Another interesting case is when $k \rightarrow \infty$ and $r = 0$. This counts the h -full numbers not exceeding x and recovers the formula

$$\gamma_{0,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}} + O\left(x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)}+\varepsilon}\right).$$

This is a much weaker version of the result of Ivić and Shiu [7], who estimate this number to be

$$\gamma_{0,h}x^{\frac{1}{h}} + \gamma_{1,h}x^{\frac{1}{h+1}} + \dots + \gamma_{h-1,h}x^{\frac{1}{2h-1}} + \Delta_h(x),$$

where $\gamma_{0,h}, \gamma_{1,h}, \dots, \gamma_{h-1,h}$ are certain computable constants and $\Delta_h(x) \ll x^\rho$ for ρ small.

Proof of Theorem 3. First, we proceed to prove Equations (14) and (17). Fix $0 < B \leq x$ (to be determined later) and suppose that $U = U_k(n)$ is such that $U \leq B$. We start by counting all the possible $L = L_k(n)$ satisfying $L \leq x/U$. Since L must be both k -free and h -full, Lemma 5 implies that the number of possible values of L is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{Q}_{k,h,q_1 \dots q_r}\left(\frac{x}{U}\right) &= \prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q_j} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{q_j^h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{1}{q_j^h}}}\right)^{-1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{p^h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{1}{p^h}}}\right) \frac{x^{\frac{1}{h}}}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}} \\ &\quad + O\left(2^r \frac{x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)}+\varepsilon}}{U^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)}+\varepsilon}}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where q_1, \dots, q_r are the primes in the factorization of U .

To make the proof easier to follow, we define

$$f(k, h) := \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{p^h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{1}{p^h}}}\right).$$

Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x \\ U_k(n) \leq B}} \Omega(U_k(n)) + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) \\ &= f(k, h)x^{\frac{1}{h}} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ U \leq B}} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}} \\ &\quad + O\left(\sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ U \leq B}} 2^{\omega(U)} \Omega(U) \frac{x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon}}{U^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon}}\right) + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that for $U \in \mathcal{N}_k$, we have $2^{\omega(U)} \leq q_1 \cdots q_r \leq U^{\frac{1}{k}}$. Using this to bound the error term above gives

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= f(k, h)x^{\frac{1}{h}} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}} \\ &\quad + O\left(x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ U \leq B}} \Omega(U) U^{\frac{1}{k} - \frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} - \varepsilon}\right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) \\ &\quad - f(k, h)x^{\frac{1}{h}} \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ B < U}} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}}. \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

We have the following estimate, analogous to Equation (28):

$$\sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x \\ B < U_k(n) \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) \leq \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ B < U \leq x}} \left\lfloor \frac{x}{U} \right\rfloor \Omega(U) \leq \sum_{\substack{U \in \mathcal{N}_k \\ U \leq x}} \frac{x}{U} \Omega(U). \tag{35}$$

Applying Lemma 4 to Equations (34) and (35), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= f(k, h)x^{\frac{1}{h}} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{q}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}} \\ &+ O\left(x^{\frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} B^{\frac{2}{k} - \frac{2h+1}{2h(h+1)} - \varepsilon} \log \log B\right) \\ &+ O\left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \log \log x\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{h}} B^{\frac{1}{k} - \frac{1}{h}} \log \log B\right). \end{aligned}$$

We choose $B = x^{\frac{k}{k+2h(h+1)}}$ and get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathcal{N}_h \\ n \leq x}} \Omega(U_k(n)) &= f(k, h)x^{\frac{1}{h}} \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{q}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}} \\ &+ O\left(x^{\frac{1}{h} - \left(\frac{k}{h} - 1\right) \frac{1}{k+2h(h+1)} + \varepsilon} \log \log x\right). \end{aligned}$$

We now proceed to find a closed expression for

$$f(k, h) \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{q}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\Omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}}.$$

We consider a generating function given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\Omega, k, h}(z) &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_k} \frac{z^{\Omega(n)}}{n^{\frac{1}{h}}} \prod_{q|n} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{q}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{p}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{z^k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} \left(1 + \frac{z}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{z^2}{p^{\frac{2}{h}}} + \dots\right)\right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{p}{h}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\frac{z^k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{z}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right), \end{aligned}$$

which is absolutely convergent over compact sets.

We will recover our term of interest by computing $\mathcal{E}'_{\Omega, k, h}(1)$, which we find by considering the logarithmic derivative:

$$\frac{\mathcal{E}'_{\Omega, k, h}(z)}{\mathcal{E}_{\Omega, k, h}(z)} = \sum_p \frac{\frac{\frac{kz^{k-1}}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} - \frac{(k-1)z^k}{p^{\frac{k+1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{z}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right)^2}}{\left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{\frac{k}{h}}}{1 - \frac{1}{\frac{p}{h}}}\right) + \frac{\frac{z^k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{z}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}}.$$

Therefore,

$$\left. \frac{\mathcal{E}'_{\Omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{E}_{\Omega,k,h}(z)} \right|_{z=1} = \sum_p \frac{\frac{k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{\frac{k+1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right)}.$$

By multiplying the above by $\mathcal{E}_{\Omega,k,h}(1)$ and by the coefficient $f(k, h)$, we get an expression for $E_{\Omega,k,h}$:

$$\begin{aligned} f(k, h)\mathcal{E}'_{\Omega,k,h}(1) &= f(k, h) \sum_p \frac{\frac{k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{\frac{k+1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right)} \\ &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{\frac{k}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} - \frac{k-1}{p^{\frac{k+1}{h}}}}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}\right)} \\ &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{kp^{\frac{1}{h}} - k + 1}{p^{\frac{k-h-1}{h}} (p^{\frac{1}{h}} - 1) (p^{1+\frac{1}{h}} + p^{\frac{1}{h}} - p)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p - p^{\frac{1}{h}}}{p^2 (p^{\frac{1}{h}} - 1)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Equations (15) and (18) are proven analogously. Here instead we must consider

$$f(k, h) \sum_{U \in \mathcal{N}_k} \prod_{q|U} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{\omega(U)}{U^{\frac{1}{h}}}.$$

The corresponding generating function is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\omega,k,h}(z) &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_k} \frac{z^{\omega(n)}}{n^{\frac{1}{h}}} \prod_{q|n} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{z}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p^{\frac{2}{h}}} + \dots\right)\right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right)^{-1} \frac{z}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} \frac{z}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}}\right), \end{aligned}$$

which is absolutely convergent.

In order to find $\mathcal{E}'_{\omega,k,h}(1)$, we consider the logarithmic derivative:

$$\frac{\mathcal{E}'_{\omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{E}_{\omega,k,h}(z)} = \sum_p \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}} + \frac{z}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}.$$

Therefore,

$$\left. \frac{\mathcal{E}'_{\omega,k,h}(z)}{\mathcal{E}_{\omega,k,h}(z)} \right|_{z=1} = \sum_p \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p}}.$$

By multiplying the above by $\mathcal{E}_{\omega,k,h}(1)$ and by the coefficient $f(k, h)$, we get an expression for $E_{\omega,k,h}$:

$$\begin{aligned} f(k, h)\mathcal{E}'_{\omega,k,h}(1) &= f(k, h) \sum_p \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p}} \prod_p \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}} \right)^{-1} \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}} \right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p}} \\ &\quad \times \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}} + \frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) \left(1 + \frac{\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k}{h}}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{h}}}} \right) \\ &= \sum_p \frac{1}{p^{\frac{k-h-1}{h}} \left(p^{1+\frac{1}{h}} + p^{\frac{1}{h}} - p \right)} \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p - p^{\frac{1}{h}}}{p^2 \left(p^{\frac{1}{h}} - 1 \right)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Theorem 3. □

Proof of Corollary 3. Recall that $n = L_k(n)U_k(n)$ and this implies

$$\Omega(n) = \Omega(L_k(n)) + \Omega(U_k(n)).$$

Combining Equations (14) and (26), we immediately obtain Equation (19). □

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